

CLIMAREST

Deliverable 2.1

Technical report on the initial stakeholder analysis based on qualitative workshops and interviews in the demonstration sites.

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Prepared by: Yennie K. Bredin and Paola Parretti			
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Lead authors	Yennie K. Bredin and Paola Parretti		
Editors	John D. C. Linnell (Norwegian Institute for Nature Research), Marc Bouchoucha (French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea), Marta Pujol (SINTEF Ocean AS), and Thea Lurås Oftebro (SINTEF Ocean AS)		

Contributing authors	<p>África Núñez (University of Malaga), Ana Dinis (The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation), Anatoly O. Sinitsyn (SINTEF AS), Francisco Silva (The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation), Hanne Kvitsand (SINTEF AS), Ida Beathe Øverjordet (SINTEF Ocean AS), João Canning Clode (The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation), João Monteiro (The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation), Juan Lugilde Yáñez (University of Galway), Laura Leyva Díaz (University of Alicante), Liam Morrison (University of Galway), Marko Radeta (MARE-ARDITI), Marisa Gouvea (The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation), Martin Perrot (SEABOOST), Pablo Sanchez-Jerez (University of Alicante), Paula Daban Losada (University of Vigo), Ricardo Bermejo (University of Malaga), Stéphane Pouvreau (French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea), and Susanne Schäfer (The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation)</p>
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Introduction

European Union Missions are innovation missions designed to tackle critical and specific challenges for Europe to achieve large-scale and long-term change. Mission Ocean is arranged in Lighthouses with focus on specific topics to achieve a healthy and restored ocean by 2030. The Missions are intended to demonstrate the way for follow-up projects that work along the entire value chain for smart solutions and a sustainable future. As such the CLIMAREST Mission Ocean project aims to guide nature-based innovations and the restoration of degraded marine coastal ecosystems to provide sustainable solutions for healthy and resilient coastal communities and ecosystems.

The 55,000 km long coastline of Europe hosts over 40% of its population and includes the Arctic and Atlantic basins. In these areas, heterogeneous human communities see marine and coastal environments as being strongly interconnected. However, the same areas and their ecosystems are also strongly affected by the twin crises of climate change and biodiversity loss. These affect the resilience of coastal and marine socio-ecological systems. In fact, European citizens already face increased climate instability, a rise in natural disasters such as landslides, floods, fires, heatwaves, hurricanes, and droughts, and a loss of biodiversity and socio-ecological resilience. There is therefore an urgent need to protect and restore ecosystem resilience and the biodiversity that these ecosystems depend upon, c.f. the United Nations' declaration of the years 2021-2030 as the "Decade on Ecosystem Restoration".

Ecosystem restoration is an integrated and interdisciplinary action that requires a combination of disciplines such as biology, geology, engineering, sociology, and economics to grasp the complexity of the socio-ecological system and its responses to both disturbances and mitigation efforts. Ecosystem restoration is also embedded within the United Nations' World Health Organization's "One Health"- approach, in its recognition of the interconnectedness of human health and wellbeing with ecosystem integrity and biodiversity health. Given the urgency of the twin crises, however, and the fast-approaching deadline of 2030 for not only the Decade initiative, but also the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Union Biodiversity Strategy, and the Post-2020 biodiversity targets, there is an urgent need to develop and test new innovations in selected coastal ecosystems where restoration actions will secure the highest impact and provide joint solutions for restoring marine and coastal ecosystems and increasing socio-ecological resilience.

Restoring marine and coastal ecosystems and increasing socio-ecological resilience require an integration of both human and institutional components. The effectiveness of restoration projects thus depends on appropriate restoration protocols, monitoring, and stakeholder engagement. Similarly, the success of a restoration operation depends on stakeholders' commitment to its objectives. Real collaboration with local citizens is therefore key in defining restoration objectives, achieving lasting restoration goals, ensuring responsible data collection, and allowing for respectful, creative, and efficient use of local knowledge. In this context, Deliverable 2.1 presents the first steps toward a holistic approach that is mindful of local socio-ecological conditions and the perspectives of relevant actors in developing methodological approaches to deploying technological, logistical, social,

and economic innovations in the restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems from Svalbard in the High-Arctic (79°N) to Madeira in the North Atlantic (33°N).

In the following sections we describe each of the five focal ecosystems of the CLIMAREST project. These include Arctic wild and urban coastal areas in Svalbard, Norway, seagrass meadows in Ireland, European native oyster reefs in Brittany, France, soft bed benthic habitats in Vigo, Spain, and shallow water rocky bottoms in Madeira, Portugal. We briefly describe the coastal contexts in which each demonstration site exists, the sensitivity of these ecosystems to disturbances, including the historical and current pressures that have either caused the ecological degradation or inhibit ecosystem recovery, and the role that the restored ecosystems could play as major drivers of habitat complexity and foundations of oceanic biodiversity. Because effective conservation and successful ecosystem restoration on meaningful scales will depend on societal support and on a broad stakeholder and citizen engagement in the restoration process, the emphasis of this report is on the different social actors and key stakeholders in each of the areas.

A critical aspect in stakeholder engagement is to identify relevant stakeholders and audit their general and specific concerns. Similarly, citizen participation is generally dependent on the communication strategies and engagement mechanisms used. Based on qualitative workshops and interviews in the demonstration sites and online, this report provides an initial stakeholder analysis outlining who the relevant actors are in each demonstration site, and the mechanisms by which these actors may either be affected or affect the success of restoration activities.

To identify relevant stakeholders in each of the demonstration sites, we began by distributing an online survey to the demonstration teams (Linnell et al., 2023). In this survey we asked the teams about the sites, the historical and current pressures on the focal systems and species, who the people that lived and operated in the area were and about their different activities. We asked the demonstration teams to outline the managerial and legal environments of their sites to know who has tenure rights or other stakes in the area. We asked how the planned restoration activities would affect the current and future use of the areas and resources. This approach allowed us to construct a comprehensive understanding of the socio-ecological landscapes, delineating the diverse actors and communities involved in each demonstration site (c.f. König et al., 2021; Reed et al., 2009; Reed & Curzon, 2015).

Going further with the initial lists of actors we asked the demonstration teams about the potential interest and influence of the different actors. By placing the actors within an interest-influence matrix we were able to prioritise among them and identify stakeholders that would be key to involve in different ways and at different stages of the project (c.f. König et al., 2021; Reed et al., 2009; Reed & Curzon, 2015). This initial exercise resulted in the identification of 41 stakeholder groups across three categories in the five demonstration sites. The three categories were i) regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources in the study area, ii) commercial/professional users, and iii) recreational users. Following this first round of stakeholder mapping, further examinations, and initial contacts with stakeholders in the demonstration sites lead to the expansion of our list of stakeholders and the addition of a fourth stakeholder category: iv) education, schools, research, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). The results of this stakeholder analysis, including the links between different stakeholders and the restoration actions is presented in this report.

To ensure that stakeholders and citizens (continue to) take part in the different steps of the restoration efforts demonstrated within CLIMAREST (i.e., diagnosis, setting restoration goals and in restoration activities), this initial stakeholder analysis will be followed by intensive fieldwork within each demonstration site. Through this subsequent fieldwork we will explore the usefulness of different methods in reaching and engaging with diverse stakeholder groups across the socio-ecological settings of the demonstration sites.

Arctic fjord ecosystems – Svalbard, Norway

Coastal context and sensitivity to disturbances

Arctic marine ecosystems face several challenges due to global warming and local anthropogenic disturbances. Due to the location of Arctic fjords at the interface between land and ocean, the polar climate and high seasonality (e.g., no light for 4-5 months), Arctic fjord ecosystems and permafrost coastlines are vulnerable to external stressors like global warming, pollution, fishing, and the establishment of new species.

In the Arctic, erosion is the main process that shape permafrost coastlines (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 2008). Climate change intensifies coastal erosion in polar regions. This is due to increased storminess and wave heights, raising air and sea surface temperatures that prolong the open-water period, and the thawing of permafrost landscapes (Sinitsyn et al., 2020). Consequently, observations in the last decades show that rates of erosion have increased with between 80% and 160% in most monitoring sites (Lantuit et al., 2012). Future climate projections for the 21st century point to higher environmental stresses and hence possible further increase in land losses due to heightened erosion along permafrost coastlines. This would in turn lead to increased release of particulate matter and pollutants from eroding coastlines as well as other negative impacts for flora, fauna, human activities, and built infrastructure (Farquharson et al., 2018).

Adding to the negative impacts of increased coastal erosion, Arctic fjord ecosystems also experience increased pressure from anthropogenic activities. Several studies have demonstrated a decline in species diversity and abundance in Arctic fjord systems, in particular due to wastewater pollution during recent decades. There is thus an urgent need to implement both climate change and pollution discharge mitigation measures to protect Arctic marine ecosystems, and to support climate resilient human infrastructure in the High-Arctic, where the impacts of climate changes are already felt and where they are predicted to accelerate much faster than at lower latitudes.

Restoration actions and benefits

Reducing pressures on Arctic marine ecosystems will facilitate their resilience against ongoing climate change. Preventing deterioration of the marine ecosystem and promoting sustainable industry will improve future climate resilience in the Arctic society. Solutions for coastal protection will increase the climate resilience of coastal communities.

Svalbard has logistical advantages as an Arctic test site, simplifying the conduct of research and development of innovation actions. The restoration of coastal sites after coal mine closure is completed at the Svea mine and is under discussion for mines closer to the regional capital, Longyearbyen. Ecological restoration in Svalbard may thus benefit from ongoing experiences with stakeholders, the development of monitoring methods for the coastal terrestrial environment, and potential erosion control measures on the road to/from the Svalbard airport, in coastal areas within the town boundaries, and of historical buildings and constructions. Moreover, implementation of different wastewater treatment strategies in the two largest settlements in Svalbard and ongoing work to improve water quality, makes for a golden opportunity to join forces with the local authorities to reduce discharge impacts on the fjord ecosystem.

These factors make Svalbard ideal for developing tools that are applicable under Arctic climatic conditions, for enhancing human community resilience through nature-based solutions that prevent coastal erosion in built environments, and for mitigating Arctic marine ecosystem pressures from discharge of untreated sewage.

Nature based coastal protection to reduce erosion in permafrost shorelines.

Coastal erosion of permafrost coastlines in urban settings is a natural process that may accelerate due to climate change, and local human influence on the coast, e.g., by the construction of structures that interrupt sediment transport. Because increased erosion rates in Svalbard threaten urban settlements, erosion rates along the Longyearbyen coastline must be halted. Additional benefits that may come from installing a nature-based solution to reduce the effect of erosion on an anthropized system along the coast of Longyearbyen may include reduced anthropogenic impacts on biodiversity, improved ecosystem management, the maintenance of human subsistence, and the protection of cultural heritage in the coastal zone (Gann et al., 2019).

To mitigate coastal erosion in Longyearbyen the following activities will be developed by CLIMAREST:

- A vision for development of the area between the City quay (“Bykaia”) and the Old quay (“Gammelkaia”). Coastal protection, biodiversity friendly development, and considerations of the social needs in the area will be main elements of the vision. The area between the City quay and the Old quay is located in the central part of the coastal area in Longyearbyen. It is a reclaimed area (artificial landfill, sandy coast) that is exposed to erosion.
- Development and construction of a representative part of the vision, i.e., construction of a blueprint/prototype in the area between the City quay and the Old quay.
- A vision for the local replication site Hiorthhamn. Hiorthhamn is a cultural heritage site situated 3 km from Longyearbyen on a sedimentary coastline. It is a unique ensemble of archeological and cultural heritage buildings. Several of these objects are threatened by significant coastal erosion (approximately 2 m/year).

Local actors and key stakeholders

The city of Longyearbyen is the biggest settlement in Svalbard, and Ny-Ålesund is a year-around research station. Together about 2 500 people live here (Statistics Norway, 2023). Most inhabitants are between 20 and 44 years old and the population is highly transient as most adult workers have short-term contracts for only a few years. There is a combined primary and secondary school in Svalbard, and although an upper secondary school is available, some families move to mainland Norway for their children to complete upper secondary school. There is a university centre (The University Centre in Svalbard; UNIS). Tourism is one of the main industries (Norwegian Ministry of Justice and Public Security, 2016). In addition, trade, logistics, research, coal mining and energy are important.

Considering the population and economic activities in Svalbard, the most important stakeholder groups that may either affect or could be affected by the implementation of erosion control measurements along the coastline of Longyearbyen include local government, commercial actors, recreational groups, and research and education. Local government stakeholders constitute Longyearbyen Community Council (“Longyearbyen Lokalstyre”) and its sections for Port of Longyearbyen (“Longyearbyen havn”), and Area Planning and Development (“Plan og utvikling”), the

Governor of Svalbard, the Svalbard Museum, and the Directorate for Cultural Heritage. Commercial stakeholders are Visit Svalbard (the tourism association for Svalbard and Longyearbyen that includes hotels, restaurants, and tourist operators), the Svalbard Business Association, and Store Norske Spitsbergen Kulkompani AS (SNSK, a Norwegian coal mining company based in Longyearbyen). Recreational groups, research, and education stakeholders include scientists and students at The University Centre in Svalbard, children in kindergartens and schools, the association Active in the outdoors ("Aktiv i friluft") which is part of Svalbard Turn (Svalbard Turn, 1930), a sports organisation in Longyearbyen, and governed by Longyearbyen Community Council, several sport clubs for diving, kayaking, etc., year-round residents, and tourists. The Active in the outdoors association embraces a variety of activities such as hiking, coastal cleaning campaigns, overnighing tours, and more (Aktiv i friluft, 2023).

Workshops and interviews

A co-design workshop about the coastal protection prototype was arranged for stakeholders in Longyearbyen on September 5th, 2023. The workshop was announced two weeks prior to its date in the local newspaper SvalbardPosten (print version, desktop, and mobile app), on LinkedIn, on Facebook where an event was created in the group for positive remarks and information in Longyearbyen ("Ros og Info Longyearbyen"), through flyers in the library of Longyearbyen, and in the calendar, website, and Facebook page of Longyearbyen Community Council ("Longyearbyen Lokalstyre"), the public authority.

Twenty-five people came for the event. They came from Longyearbyen Community Council and its section for Areal Planning and Development), an engineering consultancy for civil infrastructure, logistics operators in Svalbard, long-timers (i.e., locals who have lived in Svalbard for more than one decade), Visit Svalbard, international scientists, students, and locals who have lived in Svalbard for less than 10 years. The group was evenly divided between men and women (we did not ask about, neither aimed to nor tried to identify the intermediate genders). Most people were between 25 and 60 years old (45%). One quarter were between 20 and 25 years old (25%) and one fifth (20%) were older than 60 years old.

During the meeting potential focal areas for the interventions were presented and discussed. The area between the City quay and the Old quay in Longyearbyen was presented as the place for the development and installation of the coastal protection prototype. The reference sites, i.e., Hiorthhamn, Revneset and Vestpynten were not presented in the meeting due to time limits (figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of erosion retention sites in Svalbard, Norway. A) Revneset, B) Hiorthhamn, C) Longyearbyen and D) Vestpynten.

Main concerns raised by the stakeholders were related to social needs. One participant summarized this by commenting that the Old quay had been a place of life where people met when a boat was coming. The participant remembered those times as happy moments, remarking that such an area with a vibe that is similar to the past vibe of the Old quay is currently missing in Longyearbyen. This is partly conditioned by the governance of the coastal zone where all large quay facilities (for the docking of large vessels) are fenced and do not allow free access. It is therefore no longer possible for people to meet at the quay and wait for the boats to arrive.

As a solution to this lack of social "infrastructure" the participants suggested that the area between the City quay and the Old quay in Longyearbyen, could be developed into an area that would be suitable for recreation for all. The stakeholders also gave feedback and expressed interest in the CLIMAREST prototype. They provided several technical comments on how to make the designs better, but no negative critique. Suggestions included ensuring sufficient space for the docking of small boats and other activities, and to avoid the fencing of viewpoints (a different safety solution would still be needed to assure safety). A take home message from the co-design workshop was that a recreational element needs to be incorporated into the prototype. This may be operationalized as a small spin-off project.

Mechanisms by which stakeholders may affect or be affected by restoration activities

Figure 2. Stakeholders diagram about erosion control of permafrost coastlines in Svalbard, Norway. Pressures on the fjord ecosystem are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist in 1) monitoring the coastline; 2) creating vision for the whole coastal stretch between the City quay and the Old quay and constructing a representative part of it, i.e. building a blue-grey hybrid prototype solution for coastal protection to halt/control the erosion rate and restoring part of a typical coastal habitat in Adventfjorden and Isfjorden (the fjords in proximity of Longyearbyen); 3) creating visions for coastal protection prototypes in Hiothhamn; and 4) creating visions (i.e. investigation opportunities) for expanding the prototype in Longyearbyen, e.g. for implementing it in other parts of the town (along the eroding road to Svalbard airport and at the cultural heritage site at Hotellneset (the Swedish barracks)). Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

The Port of Longyearbyen authority is a key stakeholder at "the City quay – the Old quay" site as they are responsible for the site (right side, figure 2). This is the stakeholder that will take ultimate decisions on the vision and approaches for developing the area between the City quay and the Old quay (grey line between "Blue-grey hybrid solution" and Port of Longyearbyen, right side, figure 2).

The Port of Longyearbyen authority is interested in converting the area between the City quay and the Old quay into a thriving area that accommodates the needs of the inhabitants of Longyearbyen, the port, and nature. The current vision includes a marina for small boats and a promenade, both built with the re-use of wood from decommissioned mines in Svea (Svalbard). Port of Longyearbyen seems to be positive toward developing a part of this area to be more natural. Overall, development of the area, should it be successful, will be positive for Port of Longyearbyen (right side, figure 2).

From the discussions during the co-design workshop, it became clear that the other stakeholders may not wish for a new marina but would rather have more natural areas. There are thus different recreational interests at play and there is a need for deciding on what interests to prioritize. Although there are no current activities in the area between the City quay and the Old quay that would be negatively affected by its development, people became agitated when others suggested things that they were not interested in. Developing the area between the City quay and the Old quay for particular recreational interests or others may thus give rise to potential conflicts of interests.

The final approval of construction in the area is under the governance of Longyearbyen Community Council and its section for Area Planning and Development (grey line between "Blue-grey hybrid solution" and the Area Planning and Development authority, right side, figure 2).

Citizens of Longyearbyen may benefit if the area between the City quay and the Old quay is developed to their needs (green line between Blue-grey hybrid solution and Citizens, middle, figure 2). At the same time, citizens may influence the vision and approaches for development of the area (middle, figure 2). They may also take part in monitoring of coastal change in the area through photography (should protection be installed or not), this will, to some degree, allow citizens to influence the prototype development in the area (grey line between Citizens and Monitoring, left, figure 2).

The visions for Hiorthhamn may positively affect the Svalbard Museum, the Directorate for Cultural Heritage, the Governor of Svalbard, Visit Svalbard, and citizens as it will offer an opportunity for saving this historical site from coastal erosion (lower left, figure 2). Eventual erosion control in Hiorthhamn will provide preservation of sufficient historical value (some amount of value may be lost in the process of protection), and it will be a reason to use the site as a driver contributing to sustainable development of Longyearbyen (green lines from Visions for Hiorthhamn to these stakeholders, left side, figure 2). Svalbard museum, The Directorate for Cultural Heritage, the Governor of Svalbard, Visit Svalbard (to some degree), and citizens (to some degree) have the mandate to influence the visions and eventual erosion control measures at Hiorthhamn (grey lines from Visions for Hiorthhamn to these stakeholders, left side, figure 2).

In the winter of 2021, Longyearbyen Community Council together with Longyearbyen Cinema Club and Active in the outdoors organised an outdoor cinema viewing at the historical cable car station in Hiorthhamn. A wall of the cable car station was used as a screen. This event was a success. Hence, one may expect that there is support for the efforts to preserve this area. Tourist companies and locals (individually and through the Svalbard Sailing Association; "Svalbard Seilforening") also make kayak tours to Hiorthhamn. They are therefore interested in keeping this point of cultural interest and would be supportive of efforts to preserve the area. The trail most commonly used for the Svalbard ski marathon also lies in proximity to Hiorthhamn (Svalbard Turn, 2023), hence participants (around 600 people, both tourists and locals) may enjoy viewing the symbolic building of the cable car station in Hiorthhamn.

The University Centre of Svalbard, students in Longyearbyen schools, and tourists may help monitor coastal change at both the area between the City quay and the Old quay and in Hiorthhamn (should protection be installed or not). This will, to some degree, provide influence of these stakeholders on the vision(s) and the prototype(s) in these areas (left side, figure 2).

Two logistical operators, Pole Position and Bring, are also located in the area, and may be interested in knowing about the developments happening next to them.

Visit Svalbard (lower middle, figure 2) participated in the co-design workshop, held in Longyearbyen on September 5th. They shared a book called *The coastal path in Longyearbyen – short journey experiences in nature and culture*, which provides an overview over attractions rooted in nature and culture along the coastline in Longyearbyen and around (Frantzen & Bakken, 2017). The coastal stretch between the City quay and the Old quay is also described in this publication. It is noted that the area hosts several logistical facilities (warehouses), a path from the harbour to the city centre (for tourists that arrive by cruise ships to town), mooring facilities for sail boats, it is a habitat for a few bird species, and that the area needs to be cleaned from the cluttering of some industrial garbage (concrete plates, etc.).

The visions for both the area between the City quay and the Old quay and Hiorthhamn may positively contribute to the activities of different actors within the Svalbard Business Association as the areas that become protected against coastal erosion may provide opportunities for economic activities (green lines going from Vision for Longyearbyen and Visions for Hiorthhamn to Svalbard Business Association, bottom, figure 2). At the same time different actors within this association may have conflicting interests, and not all the interests may be included in the visions. Hence, certain conflicts may arise.

[Improve Arctic wastewater management for ecosystem protection.](#)

Longyearbyen and the nearby research community at Ny-Ålesund (B and A respectively, figure 3) host a combined population of over 2 500 people (Statistics Norway, 2023). Longyearbyen is the largest of the two settlements. In December 2022, a sieve was installed here for mechanical removal of large particulate waste in wastewater coming from Longyearbyen to mitigate discharge of macro-pollutants to the fjord. Although the sieve stops macro-waste like wet wipes from coming into the fjord, microplastics, other chemicals, and human waste is still let out. Therefore, the sieve is not enough to stop pollutants from leaking into the fjord. To remedy wastewater pollution from Longyearbyen a social campaign directed towards local citizens and tourists will be designed to inform and encourage people in Longyearbyen to be conscious about what they flush down the toilets. To measure the impact of the social campaign, Ny-Ålesund, where a full-scale biological treatment facility was installed in 2018, will serve as a reference site.

Figure 3. Location of the wastewater mitigation sites in Svalbard. A) Ny-Ålesund, B) Longyearbyen.

Local actors and key stakeholders

Based on the stakeholder mapping, the relevant governance stakeholders are Longyearbyen Community Council and the Governor of Svalbard. Relevant commercial stakeholders are Visit Svalbard, Svalbard Museum, the Svalbard Airport, Coop (the local supermarket), plumbers, commercial fisheries, and the association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO). Relevant research and educational stakeholders are research cruises, researchers and students at The University Centre in Svalbard, and children in kindergartens and schools. In addition, year-round residents, and tourists are important.

Workshops and interviews

The case coordinator has been in contact with the Longyearbyen Community Council and with plumbers. Primary contact has been through Teams meetings, physical meetings in Longyearbyen and through emails. There has also been contact with the University Centre in Svalbard, related to conducting field data sampling campaigns during the summer of 2023. Follow up one-on-one meetings are planned for with Longyearbyen Community Council to develop the social campaigns, as the Community Council is the owner and operator of the wastewater system, with the plumbers and with the University Centre in Svalbard. Contact with other stakeholders are ongoing, and the development of social campaigns against sewage pollution has been initiated. These will be implemented during the spring of 2024.

Mechanisms by which stakeholders may affect or be affected by restoration activities

Figure 4. Stakeholders diagram about sewage remedy in Svalbard, Norway. Pressures on the fjord ecosystem are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist in 1) developing a social campaign and 2) monitoring the effect of the social campaign. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); dotted grey represent possible influence; green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

The involvement of the Longyearbyen Community Council is essential and will be beneficial in the development and implementation of a social campaign and in monitoring its effect. Longyearbyen Community Council is the owner of the wastewater system and responsible for the wastewater discharge to the fjord. They are thus a key stakeholder (middle, figure 4). The Community Council has an allowance of discharge of wastewater to the fjord stated by the Governor at Svalbard in 2007 (right, figure 4). According to the allowance, the municipality must survey the ecological and chemical status of the fjord every three years and evaluate impacts from wastewater and pollution on the local ecosystem.

The Longyearbyen Community Council uses the company Assemblin for plumbing work. The Community Council will therefore have economic benefit from improved wastewater management

by means of improved operation of the systems through less waste in the sewage. The plumbers will benefit directly from improved wastewater management and reduced waste as this will reduce the frequency of the messy, uncomfortable, and potentially hazardous (particularly during winter) operations needed to clean the system from waste plugging the pumps and pipes. The plumbers of Longyearbyen will thus be a key stakeholder group for monitoring the effects of the social campaign (middle, figure 4). Longyearbyen Community Council will benefit economically from the reduced need of cleaning operations by the plumbers. At the same time as less waste down the toilets mean less pollution into the fjord, it also means that the waste needs to be dealt with in some other way. The Longyearbyen Community Council is responsible for the garbage management, and they already ship the approximately 80 kg of waste trapped by the sieve every week to Tromsø. This is more expensive than letting the waste into the fjord, but the ecological benefits outweigh the economic cost.

Other stakeholders like Coop, schools, Visit Svalbard, and the Airport will contribute to spreading information about the sewage system in Svalbard. Their active involvement may positively influence the restoration action (left side, figure 4). Commercial fisheries in connecting fjords (right, figure 4) are interested in the results from the project but will not take part in monitoring or deployment of the social campaign themselves.

The young citizens of Longyearbyen are one of the main targets of the social campaign (left side, figure 4). They will benefit from increased knowledge and awareness about the impacts of human activities on the Arctic fjord Adventfjorden, including increased knowledge about the local sewage system and how wastewater is (not) treated. The aim is that children and students will share the acquired information at home, involving their families in this action. We will also conduct an ocean literacy campaign at the school in Longyearbyen, aiming to increase the ocean literacy among the school children.

There are approximately 150 000 tourists visiting Longyearbyen annually, with an average length of stay of approximately 2 days (Hovelsrud et al., 2023). Tourists are thus a key target group of the social campaign, in addition to the young citizens of Longyearbyen. Tourists will be indirectly involved in the social campaign. Their collaboration depends on the active involvement of Visit Svalbard, the Airport, and the Port of Longyearbyen (lower middle, figure 4).

The Port of Longyearbyen and all related activities (i.e., fishers and cruises) may only marginally affect the result of the social campaign when ship crews come ashore (lower middle, figure 4).

Seagrass ecosystems – Galway Bay and Tralee Bay, Ireland

Coastal context and sensitivity to disturbances

Seagrass refers to various genera of plants, such as *Zostera*, *Halodule*, *Cymodocea*, *Posidonia*. Seagrass meadows are sediment bottoms densely colonized by seagrasses and are considered as some of the most valuable systems on earth in terms of ecosystem service provisioning, including the sequestration of carbon and nutrients (Costanza et al., 1997; Hemminga & Duarte, 2000; Lavery et al., 2013). Unfortunately, a variety of human pressures led to an accelerated loss of seagrass

meadows, globally, in the 20th century (Waycott et al., 2009). Eutrophication associated with the intensification of agriculture, habitat destruction, and waste effluent from urban areas have affected seagrass meadows negatively. With the implementation of the European Union water framework directive, environmental conditions have improved in recent decades, in Europe (de los Santos et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the recovery of seagrass meadows remains slow. Therefore, active restoration actions emerge as a critical nature-based solution and management tool for climate adaptation and resilience by enhancing ecosystem services, recovering ecological functions, and mitigating for seagrass habitat loss and degradation.

Restoration actions and benefits

Seagrass meadows can reduce the impact of coastal erosion by reducing wave energy and acting as a sediment trap, provide habitat for several marine organisms, buffer biogeochemical cycles (enhancement of denitrification, nutrient sequestration, mainly nitrogen and phosphorus), and play a key role in global climate regulation through the sequestration of carbon. Furthermore, seagrasses are recognised ecosystem engineers by forming meadows that harbour an important number of species. That makes seagrass meadows key for the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem functioning.

In Ireland, the expected increase in the number of estuaries affected by nutrient over-enrichment because of intensified agriculture may pose a challenge for seagrass restoration (gov.ie, 2023). Since 2016, two projects funded by the Irish Environmental Protection Agency (SEAMAT and MACROMAN; Bermejo et al., n.d., 2019) identified seagrass restoration as a critical tool for the recovery of ecological functioning and services provided by Irish estuaries. Their recovery may also limit the occurrence of opportunistic macroalgal blooms linked to coastal eutrophication. This is relevant and applicable across all European coastal and transitional waters.

Currently CLIMAREST provides the only ongoing seagrass meadow restoration actions in the bay of Galway and Tralee Bay, Ireland (figure 5). Developing successful restoration methods for seagrass recovery in these areas, by focusing on planting methods (e.g., site selection, transplants, seed germination) will allow us to develop protocols and methodologies applicable beyond the demonstration sites at larger scales. By assessing seagrass connectivity using molecular tools we will avoid disturbing genetic population structure of natural sites because of seagrass restoration actions. And, importantly, by promoting stakeholder engagement, we hope to create positive interest among recreational users (e.g., windsurfers, dog walkers, horse riders) and commercial fishermen in the experimental field sites for seagrass restoration.

Figure 5. Map showing the demonstrations sites of A) Galway Bay and B) Tralee Bay.

Local actors and key stakeholders

The main stakeholders for the two restoration sites in the bay of Galway and Tralee Bay are partly overlapping. For both Galway Bay and Tralee Bay government stakeholders include the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, the National Park and Wildlife Service, the Irish Environmental Protection Agency, and the Sustainable Water Network. In addition, the Local Authority Water Programme is relevant for the site in Tralee Bay.

Among the commercial stakeholders there is less overlap, although for both areas farmers in the coastal zone and adjacent watersheds are important. In Galway commercial stakeholders are farmers, wastewater managers, a wind surfing school, and a horse-riding school. In Tralee Bay we find scallop and oyster fishermen, the Tralee Oyster Fishery Society, the Maharees Seagrass Hatchery, Seaweed Harvesters, farmers, and the Tralee Bay Sea Angling Club.

Recreational stakeholders also differ between Galway Bay and Tralee Bay. In Galway Bay recreational stakeholders are beach users, horseback riders, surfers, the Galway Atlantaquaria (the national aquarium of Ireland), and the Friends of Barna woods and Rusheen Bay. In Tralee Bay we also find beach users, the Dingle Oceanworld Aquarium, the Fenit Coast Conservation Group, and Maharees Conservation Association.

Among educational stakeholders and NGOs there is again some overlap between Galway Bay and Tralee Bay. In both areas we find the Irish Marine institute, the University of Galway, and Coast Watch Ireland. In addition, Seasearch Ireland (a project for divers and snorkelers) is relevant for Galway Bay

(and potentially secondary schools). In Tralee Bay, the Munster Technological University, Tralee and the Irish Elasmobranch Group are additional relevant educational stakeholders.

Workshops and interviews

Most of the relevant stakeholders for both Galway Bay and Tralee Bay have been contacted, either through a formal letter, email, or over the phone. Only four non-priority stakeholders have not yet been contacted. One-on-one meetings have been held with approximately half of the stakeholders. The other half of the stakeholders have attended workshops arranged either with representatives from different stakeholder groups or with representatives from the same stakeholder group.

For the most part, the purpose of these meetings and workshops has been to inform the stakeholders about the CLIMAREST activities. With three of the governance stakeholders the purpose was to get their permission to conduct restoration activities. However, with some of the stakeholders the hope is to get them involved in the restoration activities, either directly through the planting of seagrass or the monitoring, or indirectly by helping with the dissemination activities.

Mechanisms by which stakeholders may affect or be affected by restoration activities

Figure 6. Stakeholder diagram about seagrass meadow restoration in Galway Bay, Ireland. Pressures on the seagrass are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist in 1) monitoring the water quality, 2) planting seagrass, 3) monitoring the recovery of seagrass meadows, and 4) outreach activities to inform the Irish public and share results and experiences with other potential seagrass meadow restoration sites. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

The Galway Bay demonstration site is small, and the bay stretches approximately 1 km across. There used to be seagrass meadows here, but for unclear reasons the seagrass meadows were degraded and disappeared from the bay. The exact time for this is unclear. Current threats to the re-establishment of seagrass meadows in the Galway Bay that cannot be affected within the project period include eutrophication from the agricultural sector, global warming of sea temperatures, increased frequency of extreme weather events, sea level rise, and the arrival and spread of invasive species such as the red seaweed *Gracilaria vermiculophylla* (Ohmi) Papenfuss that arrived with the oyster farming and now competes with seagrasses for space (top left, figure 6). Threats to the re-establishment of a seagrass meadow in the Galway Bay that can be affected within the project period include sufficient treatment of local wastewater (there is an outlet in the Galway Bay), avoidance of trampling of seagrass by recreational users, and increased tolerance of seagrass beds to local anoxic events (top right, figure 6).

Ensuring sufficient water quality in the bay will aid the re-establishment of the seagrass meadow in Galway Bay. The Wastewater Management in Galway is responsible for treating local sewage before discharging the wastewater into the bay. Some years ago, the treatment of the wastewater was improved. By involving the Irish Environmental Protection Agency, the Irish Marine Institute and the Sustainable Water Network in monitoring the water quality of the bay, the demonstration team hopes to ensure sufficient water quality also in the future (left side, figure 6).

The Environmental Protection Agency (left side, figure 6), as a government stakeholder, also provides valuable information regarding the locations and mapping of Irish seagrass meadows. They could benefit from the data collected in CLIMAREST to expand protection to new areas, focus on additional areas requiring monitoring, and potentially develop new programs to assist more local communities in finding and conserving new seagrass meadows.

Because of the improved water quality in the Galway Bay, the water should now be clean enough for the seagrass to recolonise its historical habitat. So far, however, this has not happened. Potentially this could be because of a lack of seagrass sources in the area to provide sufficient seeds for recolonisation. To test this hypothesis, plants are now being brought from source populations in protected areas in Connemara to see if the seagrass will re-establish. For these activities, the National Park and Wildlife Services is a key stakeholder and have given their permission for the collection of seagrass seeds in Connemara and Tralee Bay (lower right, figure 6). The Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage are also key stakeholders for these activities as they had to give their permission for the University of Galway to plant the seagrass seeds in the Galway Bay (lower right, figure 6).

Another hypothesis is that the invasive red algae *Gracilaria vermiculophylla* and other species that have colonised the habitat that became available when the seagrass disappeared from Galway Bay may have enriched the sediments and made them unsuitable for the seagrass. This may inhibit seagrass recolonisation to its former habitat. To test this hypothesis a trial is set up with the University of Malaga to test the suitability of the sediments for the seagrass.

At low tide the upper parts of the seagrass meadows in the bay becomes exposed. It is therefore popular with recreational beach users that use the area for horseback-riding and walking, in addition to the activities in shallow water like windsurfing and kayaking. Such recreational activities are a

potential threat to the re-establishment of the seagrass meadows as people may trample the establishing seagrass or remove the technical infrastructure associated with the experimental reintroductions of seagrass. To avoid potential conflicts with recreational users of the Galway Bay and potentially negative effects on the restoration efforts, horse riding schools, windsurfing schools, Friends of Barna woods and Rusheen Bay, Galway Atlantaquaria, Seasearch Ireland, and Coast Watch Ireland (which has very big network in Ireland) could help spread awareness and information about the restoration activities. Secondary schools and the University of Galway may also help with the outreach activities (bottom, figure 6). Furthermore, Galway Atlantaquaria and Friends of Barna woods and Rusheen Bay may help the University of Galway to monitor the seagrass recolonization progress (bottom right, figure 6).

Because the Galway Atlantaquaria has broad contact with different stakeholder groups including the wider public, they are a key stakeholder to partner with for monitoring seagrass meadow recovery, informing the public about the restoration activities and fostering broad societal acceptance. Similarly, because of their broad networks with several stakeholder groups the Friends of Barna woods and Rusheen Bay are key stakeholders that could help to both foster a broad acceptance for the restoration activities and push for necessary behavioural / policy changes. Perhaps in the future the Friends of Barna woods and Rusheen Bay may contribute to planting seagrass. Increased planting and protection of seagrass by multiple actors may help get the seagrass population above the critical threshold needed for the seagrass beds to withstand periodic anoxic events and for the seagrass meadows to re-establish.

Not only will the restoration activities greatly benefit from the collaboration of these stakeholders, but educational stakeholders like Coast Watch Ireland and Seasearch Ireland also stand to benefit by acquiring new, crucial information aligned with their interests, and by involving more citizens in their programs. Involvement in CLIMAREST, as stakeholders, will also provide them with additional feedback for their surveys, enhancing their scientific perspectives. Institutions such as the Irish Marine Institute and other departments at the University of Galway would further establish new partnerships and gain access to more valuable data for their own studies.

Figure 7. Stakeholder diagram about seagrass meadow restoration in Tralee Bay, Ireland. Pressures on the seagrass are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist in 1) monitoring the water quality, 2) planting seagrass, 3) monitoring the recovery of seagrass meadows, and 4) outreach activities to inform the Irish public and share results and experiences with other potential seagrass meadow restoration sites. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

The demonstration site at Tralee Bay is 16 km across (figure 5). Some of the coastal parts of the bay are included in Natura 2000 sites (Tralee Bay Complex SPA IE0004188). At this site there used to be seagrass meadows that have been degraded and disappeared. The timing and cause of this is uncertain. Current threats that inhibit the re-establishment of seagrass meadows in the area may be divided into two groups, those that cannot be affected within the project timeframe and those that can be affected within the project timeframe. Threats that cannot be affected within the project timeframe include eutrophication from the agricultural sector, global warming of sea temperatures, increased frequency of extreme weather events, sea level rise, the arrival of invasive species that may compete with the seagrass for space, erosion (possibly related to sea level rise and / or the disappearance of the seagrass meadows), and potentially unsustainable harvest rates of seagrass flowers by the local seagrass hatchery (top left and very top right, figure 7). Threats that can be affected within the project timeframe include proper treatment of local wastewater, scallop and oyster trawling, and the trampling of seagrass (lower top right, figure 7).

As in Galway Bay, good water quality is a prerequisite for seagrass re-establishment in Tralee Bay. By involving the Irish Environmental Protection Agency, the Irish Marine Institute and the Sustainable Water Network in monitoring the water quality of Tralee Bay, the demonstration team hopes to ensure sufficient water quality for seagrass re-establishment (left side, figure 7).

The National Park and Wildlife Services and the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage are once again key stakeholders for the restoration activities to take place as their permissions are needed for the University of Galway to plant seagrass in Tralee Bay (right, figure 7).

In Tralee Bay, shellfish trawling is still ongoing. Because trawling could seriously impede any restoration efforts the Tralee Oyster Fishery Society is a key stakeholder (lower left, figure 7). Through them an agreement has been made with the commercial stakeholders, such as the scallop and oyster fishery (top middle, figure 7) and the Tralee Bay Sea Angling Club (lower left, figure 7), to respect the areas where seagrass meadows exist. They have agreed to cease dredging activities for their mutual benefit, as the seagrass meadows serve as nurseries for fish and oyster larvae upon which their activities depend. This action aims to prevent potential impacts on the fish and oyster stocks in the future. The seagrass hatchery's operations could have negative consequences on the seagrass meadows if they harvest plants excessively for seed use. However, they also have the potential to positively impact the restoration process by exploring new techniques for seed restoration and sustainable seed extraction (top, figure 7).

Because the beach around Tralee Bay becomes exposed at low tide, the beach area is popular with recreational users. These recreational users may trample the upper seagrass zone or remove the experimental setups. In addition, it is common for people to drive cars cross parts of the beach during low tide (top, figure 7).

In local sand dune restoration projects where similar phenomena have been observed, specific paths have been designated for people to drive or walk. Something similar could be done in the Tralee Bay. To avoid potential conflicts with residents and recreational users, specific areas could be designated for the seagrass meadow restoration or driving, walking and horseback riding. To facilitate such an agreement the Tralee Oyster Fishery Society, the Tralee Bay Sea Angling Club, the Maharees Seagrass Hatchery, Coastal Watch Ireland, the Dingle Oceanworld Aquarium, the Fenit Coast Conservation Group, the Maharees Conservation Association, the Munster Technological University, Tralee and the Irish Elasmobranch Group, and the University of Galway could help spread awareness and information about the restoration activities (bottom left and middle, figure 7). Moreover, Coastal Watch Ireland, the Dingle Oceanworld Aquarium, the Fenit Coast Conservation Group, and the Maharees Conservation Association may help the University of Galway to monitor the seagrass bed recovery (bottom right, figure 7).

In addition to aiding the restoration work through the monitoring and outreach activities, local stakeholders also stand to benefit positively from restoration activities at some point in the future if the restoration succeeds and can be up-scaled. The stabilization of sediment resulting from these efforts may help prevent coastal erosion caused by rising sea levels and more powerful storms in these sensitive flood-prone areas. Healthier seagrass meadows can reduce water eutrophication,

bringing benefits to local water activities and fisheries. These areas heavily rely on marine resources, and cleaner waters imply greater benefits from marine activities.

Oyster reef ecosystems – Brittany, France

Coastal context and sensitivity to disturbances

The flat oyster *Ostrea edulis* is a European native species that once covered vast areas of seabed and built large reefs in European coastal waters. By the mid to late 1800's, flat oyster populations were largely damaged due to overfishing, often beyond recovery (Preston et al., 2020). Over the last century, the emergence of diseases and parasites combined with the proliferation of various predators and many human induced additional stressors have caused a dramatic decrease in the last remaining flat oyster populations. Today, this species has disappeared from many locations in Europe and is registered on the OSPAR14 list of threatened and/or declining species. Massive reduction in population size combined with the loss of reef type habitat structures have led to the almost complete disappearance of the essential ecological functions and ecosystem services that this species once supplied along our coasts. Although the species and its associated habitat have collapsed throughout Europe, it is not extinct, and a growing number of restoration initiatives are under way to restore European native oysters in significant densities to European marine ecosystems. The remaining pressures that inhibit natural recovery processes vary between sites and regions, and customized tools are needed to enable efficient large-scale restoration.

In France, Brittany stands out as hosting several of the main remaining flat oyster populations of the country (Pouvreau et al., 2023). Whereas larval spawning, spat settlement and recruitment from these populations can be regarded as quite abundant in comparison to other European sites, potentially providing a good basis for local recovery of native oyster beds. Three main pressures are currently limiting the recovering of the species and its ability to redevelop a functional habitat. These pressures are i) lack of substrate (hard structures on the otherwise soft bottoms), ii) high predation (mostly from Gilt-head bream (*Sparus aurata*) and Japanese oyster-drill (*Ocenebrellus inornatus*)) and iii) the presence of parasites (*Bonamia* and/or *Marteilia*).

Additional background pressures associated with coastal development also need to be accounted for in the processes limiting the natural recovery of the species, such as water pollution and coastal erosion. Although these pressures are more diffuse and the extent of their impact is more complex to determine, they affect the physical and chemical quality of the environment on which oysters depend but on which they also can have a significant influence.

In this context, shellfish farmers have played a crucial role in the past decades in maintaining the species. Oyster farmers have relied on a consistent supply of spat from the natural environment and have significantly contributed to restocking at a local level. In the wild, the species is presently mostly found on mixed sediments in the form of single individuals to small clumps, in densities generally ranging from 1 to less than 5 individuals per m² (Pouvreau et al., 2018). Functional biogenic reefs (density above 20 individuals per m² forming several clumps) are almost never found anymore. In this degraded situation, the species remains highly vulnerable to predation and other stressors, and it does not provide the ecological functions and ecosystem services that denser oyster beds and reefs could provide.

Within this general context, CLIMAREST focuses on two sites in which France's main remaining flat oyster populations can currently be found: Rade de Brest and Quiberon Bay. These sites differ in terms of environmental conditions, habitat sensitivity, human activity and ultimately stakeholder engagement and policies concerning flat oyster restoration.

The "banc du Roz" in rade de Brest is included in the "Aulne estuary" Natura 2000 site referenced FR5300046, and directly adjacent to the regional natural park of Armorique. As an estuarian site, the environmental conditions are both largely influenced by the freshwater input of the Aulne river and its associated catchment area, and by the specific marine ecosystem of the large, sheltered bay of Brest, home to a high diversity of human activities and sensitive habitats. In addition to the main overarching pressures described above, specific pressures on the species in this area include dredging, fishing, and intermittent poor water quality. The presence of maerl beds (a form of hard algae) and eelgrass meadows are additional important drivers to consider in the design of restoration projects. Oyster reef restoration must be designed so as not to negatively affect the spatial distribution or status of these other protected habitats.

The "banc de Penthièvre" in Quiberon Bay is included in the "Massif dunaire Gâvres - Quiberon" Natura 2000 site referenced "FR5300027", and close to the regional natural park of the "Golfe du Morbihan". It is a shallow and sheltered open bay. In addition to the main overarching pressures described above, specific pressures on the species in this area include coastal erosion processes. Restoration designs must be specifically adapted to the coexistence of a widespread oyster farming activity across the bay as well as an intense recreational use of the area for water sports (sailing, kayaking, power boats) and accommodation along the coast with associated pollution potential.

Restoration actions and benefits

Considering its critical situation, the native European oyster paradoxically shows great potential for large-scale restoration in Europe due to its promising response to various active restoration initiatives followed by rapid regrowth, especially in France. Through the further development of efficient methodologies to kickstart the formation of large-scale biogenic reefs, the European oyster and its habitat are believed to have the potential of providing significant support to nature-based solutions for climate change adaptation and the restoration of more resilient European coastlines in the coming decades.

Although no remaining large-scale native oyster reef has been found in European waters to date, the study of biogenic habitats formed by other oyster species across the world gives us a good picture of the species potential benefits for marine ecosystems and coastal populations. Oysters can create remarkable biogenic reef habitats providing many ecosystem services including support of biodiversity hotspots, water filtration, substrate and shoreline stabilization, denitrification, benthopelagic coupling, and biomass production (Pogoda et al., 2019). All of which are relevant in the specific contexts of the CLIMAREST demonstration sites in France. The project therefore aims to increase scientific knowledge on several of these benefits that could prove particularly important to tackle local environmental challenges.

In the western part of Quiberon Bay, coastal erosion threatens the Penthièvre isthmus, a single and narrow stretch of land connecting the Quiberon peninsula and Morbihan islands to the mainland. This

area is home to almost 15 000 permanent residents and over 100 000 summer residents. Countering erosion with the use of grey (technical engineering) coastal protection infrastructure has proven challenging during the past decade. Restored native European oyster reefs could serve as a complementary nature-based solution to prevent erosion by dissipating wave energy through the formation of shallows.

Due to their high filtration capacity, large-scale oyster reefs can have a significant influence on water quality and clarity, positively impacting many components of the ecosystem. In rade de Brest, improving water quality is both a major challenge and a major objective for local public institutions and site users. From a nature conservation perspective, enhanced water clarity would have a significant positive effect on other locally present habitat forming species such as maerl and seagrass, through increased photosynthetic capacity.

At both sites, restored oyster reefs would provide shelter and functional feeding, spawning and nursery grounds for other organisms impacted by shifting environmental conditions, making restored oyster reefs key for the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. Given the importance of both sites as main sources of spat for the native oyster farming industry, healthier and more resilient oyster reefs would provide a more resilient production system and support the local economy. Lastly, from a more global perspective, restored oyster reefs could play a significant role in climate regulation through carbon sequestration. The current knowledge about this species, as well as for other oyster species worldwide, suggests that this effect would mainly be generated through biodeposition processes and stabilization in underlying sediments when reefs are in good health and not degraded.

Given previous and other ongoing initiatives to restore the European oyster populations in the bays of Brest and Quiberon (figure 8), these locations offer an exceptional opportunity to build on previous work to develop successful large-scale native European oyster reef restoration tools. Not least because both the bays of Brest and Quiberon host sufficient wild oyster populations to allow for successful recruitment, growth, and performance evaluation, within the CLIMAREST timeline. By extension, tools developed for large-scale oyster reef restoration in the bays of Brest and Quiberon may also be applied in other locations to recover ecosystem functions and services. Such extensive upscaling to other areas and European countries would increase the potential adaptation for climate change resilience in Europe in terms of coastal spatial planning and risk management, support coastal aquaculture and fishing industries, and promote biodiversity conservation.

Figure 8. Map showing the demonstrations sites of A) the bay of Brest and B) the bay of Quiberon.

Local actors and key stakeholders

In the bay of Brest the main government stakeholders are the French Biodiversity Agency (“Office Français de la Biodiversité”), the management of the natural regional park of Armorique (“Parc naturel régional d’Armorique”) who are in charge of the NATURA2000 site, and the Directorate of Maritime Affairs of Finistère (“Direction des Affaires Maritimes du Finistère”). Commercial stakeholders including both fishermen engaged with dredging activities and their departmental representation committee (“Comité Départemental des Pêches Maritimes et des Élevages Marins du Finistère”), oyster farmers, the regional shellfish farmers representation committee of northern Brittany (“Comité Régional de Conchyliculture de Bretagne Nord”), and SCUBA diving associations of the bay of Brest (“Diving Club ACDC”). Recreational stakeholders include recreational fishermen, shellfish gatherers at low tide, beach users, coastal residents, and tourists (mainly in the summer). Relevant NGOs, research, and educational stakeholders are the one-person consultancy agency called “Cochet Environment” involved in the monitoring of oyster larvae in support of spat collection by oyster farmers, the Brest Oceanopolis aquarium, SEABOOST, French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea, the European Institute for Marine Studies, as well as local schools involved in the national program for ocean literacy (“Aires Marines Éducatives”).

In Quiberon Bay, relevant governance stakeholders are the French Biodiversity Agency, the group of local townships and district authority (“Auray Quiberon Terre Atlantique”), the directorate of maritime affairs of the Morbihan department (“Direction des Affaires Maritimes du Département du Morbihan”), and the Natura 2000 site management for the site of “Dunes Sauvages de Gâvres à

Quiberon” (“le Syndicat Mixte Dunes Sauvages de Gâvres à Quiberon”). Commercial stakeholders are both kite surfing and sailing schools, the regional shellfish farmers representation committee of southern Bretagne (“Comité Régional de Conchyliculture de Bretagne Sud”), the local representation committee of oyster framers in Quiberon Bay (“Syndicat Ostréicole de la Baie de Quiberon”), the oyster farmers themselves, and local producers of oyster farming equipment. Recreational stakeholders include both coastal residents and tourists (mainly in the summer season), beach users, kite surfers, sailors, and recreational fishermen including shellfish gatherers at low tide. NGOs, research, and educational stakeholders relevant in Quiberon Bay are the one-person consultancy agency called “Cochet Environment” operating critical monitoring of oyster larvae availability in support of spat collection by oyster farmers, “Ostreapolis” the local museum and education centre dedicated to oysters, local schools involved in the national program for ocean literacy (“Aires Marines Éducatives”), a recently formed NGO dedicated to native oyster reef restoration (“Action pour la Régénération en Plongée des Récifs d’Ostrea Edulis”), French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea and SEABOOST.

Workshops and interviews

As projects have already been carried out in both the bays of Brest and Quiberon, most local stakeholders have already been actively engaged in previous habitat restoration activities. Stakeholder acceptability and the administrative procedures that are required for the experimental setups are thus generally well managed.

Most of the relevant stakeholders for both the bays of Brest and Quiberon have been contacted specifically about CLIMAREST, through email or over the phone, leading to one-on-one meetings. For the most part, the purpose of these meetings has been to inform the stakeholders about the CLIMAREST objectives, activities, and possibly interesting outputs relative to the specific area of interest of the respective stakeholders. With the oyster farmers of the Quiberon Bay, the objective was also to include them in the restoration design and in the restoration field activities.

Specific authorizations and/or partnership agreements were necessary to conduct restoration activities in Quiberon Bay and will be necessary for upcoming operations in the bay of Brest in 2024. The links between these stakeholders and CLIMAREST are further defined in the next section.

Citizen stakeholders have not yet been contacted but will soon be contacted as part of the outreach actions, which comes a bit later in the project. All stakeholders will be further involved in both sites through specific workshops aimed at defining local roadmaps for upscaling the restoration.

Mechanisms by which stakeholders may affect or be affected by restoration activities

Figure 9. Stakeholder diagram about oyster reef restoration in the bay of Brest, France. Pressures on the oyster populations are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist of 1) deploying artificial reef structures, and 2) outreach activities to inform the French public and share results and experiences with other potential oyster reef restoration sites. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

Figure 10. Stakeholder diagram about oyster reef restoration in Quiberon Bay, France. Pressures on the oyster populations are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist of 1) deploying artificial reef structures, and 2) outreach activities to inform the French public and share results and experiences with other potential oyster reef restoration sites. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, red indicates a negative effect, and orange indicates a potential conflict.

Both sites, in the bays of Brest (figure 9) and Quiberon (figure 10), are embedded in complex stakeholder environments, composed of public institutions, private economic actors, leisure practitioners and scientific and technical organisations. For the bay of Brest, CLIMAREST restoration actions are carried out on the “banc du Roz”, for which French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea already has authorizations to carry out experimental work, in the framework of a wider partnership with the French biodiversity agency (left, figure 9). For Quiberon Bay, SEABOOST established a specific partnership agreement with the regional shellfish farmers representation committee of southern Bretagne to carry out restoration actions on the “banc de Penthièvre”, which is a marine plot under their management for wild oyster conservation purposes (middle, figure 10). In both sites, the restoration actions must be consistent with local regulations and policies regarding i) deployment of structures on the seabed, and ii) restoration of marine habitats. Permits must be obtained from the directorates of marine affaires and agreed upon with local Natura 2000 management institutions. These institutions are therefore key stakeholders (left, figure 9; left and right, figure 10). The French Biodiversity Agency is also involved to approve the general approach of actively restoring the European oyster. As this institution defines the ecosystem restoration policy throughout the country it is a key stakeholder (figure 9; figure 10). For both sites, implementing active

restoration has been found relevant since several years of observations have demonstrated that the species is incapable of spontaneous reef formation (Pouvreau et al., 2020). One-on-one meetings were carried out with all government stakeholders in the first months of CLIMAREST (January to April 2023) to inform them about the demonstration sites' objectives, determine the specific conditions in which restoration operations could be undertaken, and obtain the necessary approvals prior to field operations that were already initiated in May 2023 for the bay of Brest and June 2023 for Quiberon Bay. The government stakeholders will be further informed on the results of the restoration activities. They will also be involved in workshops to determine local roadmaps for upscaling (grey and green arrows between the application of artificial reef structures and these stakeholders, figure 9; figure 10).

In both sites, it is the responsibility of local municipalities to treat urban wastewater and provide solutions for coastal defence. As such, these stakeholders could have a direct interest in some of the ecosystem services provided by restored oyster reefs, especially in water filtration and mitigation of coastal erosion. They are therefore interested in the results of CLIMAREST on these subjects and will be mobilized in the definition of upscaling roadmaps as possible direct beneficiaries of restoration as a nature-based solution (left, figure 9; left, figure 10). They are very influential politically, and they could significantly contribute to upscaling in a follow-up project to CLIMAREST.

Oyster farmers and their representation committees are key stakeholders in both sites and were involved early in the restoration processes (middle, figure 9; left and middle, figure 10). Their economic activities are highly dependent on restoring healthy wild stocks to guarantee a stable and plentiful spatfall. They have been the major contributor to the species' conservation during the past decades through self-imposed restrictions on their production activities. Furthermore, their technical experience with oyster production is directly mimicked in the restoration activities. As such, their engagement for future restoration operations is critical to guarantee technical, political, and possibly financial support toward upscaling. These stakeholders were involved in one-on-one meetings and workshops in the Quiberon Bay area. The workshops for this first period of CLIMAREST had the objective of getting their feedback on technical aspects of structure design, deployment feasibility and restoration planning. They were also involved in field operations for the deployment of artificial settlement substrates and providing vessels for the June 2023 operation. They will be further involved in CLIMAREST for upcoming substrate deployment campaigns, studies on the contribution of their production systems to the support of wild oyster populations, as well as to participate in determining upscaling roadmaps, in collaboration with other stakeholders. Their engagement for nature conservation purposes is a sensitive issue as their relationships with nature conservation institutions can be conflictual. They have been a driving force for maintaining the species present in the past, but this has been done mainly from a shellfish production perspective and mostly on their own terms. Introducing nature conservation and other ecosystem services objectives changes both their autonomy in managing the resource and associated management practices. Efficient communication on common benefits of oyster reef restoration and the importance of restorative aquaculture models will be key for upcoming workshops involving a wider range of stakeholders.

Producers of oyster farming equipment have been contacted for purchase of their goods and services for the development and deployment of reef enhancing structures. These specialised stores / service providers would benefit from upscaling restoration efforts through increase in demand for their materials (left, figure 10).

Although professional fishermen are not very active in the area where the restoration takes place in the Quiberon Bay, they interact a little more with the restoration process in the bay of Brest. Restoration efforts and upscaling strategies must be consistent with pressures that still occur on the seabed, and dredging activity is still an important pressure in some areas of the bay of Brest. Professional fishermen could however benefit from the contribution of large-scale oyster reef restoration to certain fish and shellfish stocks (upper left, figure 9).

Recreational users have not yet been very involved. In Quiberon Bay, although they are not impacted (or at least not significantly) by the CLIMAREST actions themselves, they could be significantly impacted by future upscaling. Regenerating shallows and reefs is likely to affect water sports both negatively (restricted areas due to navigation hazards) and positively (fight against coastal erosion and protection of coastal infrastructures; bottom, figure 10) whereas boosting biodiversity will be beneficial to professional and recreational fisheries (left and middle, figure 9). So far, local sailing clubs and kite surfing schools have been informed of the CLIMAREST operations as part of a navigation hazard awareness campaign based on informal one-on-one meetings to let them know where the structures are deployed and how they are marked at the surface. The targeted benefits of upscaling were communicated to them. Recreational users will be involved later in the restoration process as contributors in upscaling roadmaps workshops.

More generally, both residents and tourists have a shared interest in the condition of the environment (middle, figure 9; left, figure 10). Recreational fishermen and shellfish gatherers are an example of a subgroup of citizen stakeholders that would directly benefit from oyster reef restoration and associated effects on biodiversity and stocks (middle, figure 9). The contribution of restored reefs to the environmental quality could be a positive driver for upscaling and local political lobbying. Tourists can be a significant source of income for small oyster farmers. Although there is not yet a high demand for European flat oysters (as compared to the more commercially widespread Pacific oyster), some flat oyster farmers are working to increase consumer interest in the future. Revaluing the species in local consumer circles could also create economic/political incentives for upscaling restoration. Citizens will be involved later in the restoration process through various actions including dedicated school interventions to promote ocean literacy and public awareness of coastal habitat conservation and restoration. The national program for ocean literacy in French schools supports an increase in ocean literacy for marine biodiversity by taking children out to nearby coastal sites and involving them in small management actions. Two schools involved in this program are close to the two demo sites (one for each area), and specific outreach actions will be undertaken (right, figure 9; right, figure 10). CLIMAREST actions and more general marine restoration will also be promoted within a master's program at the university of Brest.

Finally, there are several scientific and technical stakeholders that are involved in the development and evaluation of these restoration initiatives. SEABOOST and French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea are part of these, alongside local universities and consultancies providing various services for the monitoring of the marine environment (middle and right, figure 9; right, figure 10). Local aquariums (Oceanopolis in Brest) or museums (Ostreapolis near Quiberon) contribute to outreach about the species by hosting for example events or exhibitions. These institutions will be mobilized for specific outreach activities in CLIMAREST. In the Quiberon Bay area, a recently formed NGO ("Action pour la Régénération en Plongée des Récifs d'Ostrea Edulis"), wishes to promote oyster

restoration in neighbouring areas and is currently developing a project off the nearby island of Houat. CLIMAREST will support this initiative by providing expert advice and good practice guidelines.

Sedimentary soft bed ecosystems – Vigo, Spain

Coastal context and sensitivity to disturbances

In Vigo there is a type of estuary, commonly known as rias. The term originates from the Galician word "ría," which itself is derived from "río" (river). Rias are found along the entire Galician coast in Spain. Initially, the term was specifically used to describe submerged river valleys that were formed parallel to the geological structure of the surrounding rock and ran perpendicular to the coastline. Over time, the definition of ria was broadened to include other flooded river valleys, regardless of the geological structure of the surrounding rock. Naturally the rias are sedimentary soft bed ecosystems with mudflats and sandbanks. The presence of extensive mudflats and sandbanks provides important habitats for various invertebrates, crustaceans, and migratory birds. Seagrass meadows are common in the shallower areas of rias. These habitats serve as nurseries for many fish species and provide shelter for various marine organisms. The rocky shores along the ria offer attachment points for algae, barnacles, and other sessile organisms. These areas contribute to the overall biodiversity of the ecosystem. This ecosystem is also influenced by the northern part of the Canary Current upwelling. Because of these upwellings the rias of Galicia have one of the highest primary production levels along the European coasts, making it one of the regions with the highest shellfish production in the world, and host to the largest mussel aquaculture industry in Europe. This activity affects the local communities in various ways.

Mussel production, with rafts locally called "bateas", can have various effects on the sea bottom and surrounding environment. Mussel rafts can contribute to increased sedimentation in the areas where they are deployed. Organic matter, such as mussel faeces, can accumulate on the seabed beneath the rafts. This organic enrichment and deposition of organic material from mussel rafts can influence benthic communities. Increased nutrients may lead to changes in the composition of sediment-dwelling organisms, potentially favouring species that thrive in nutrient-rich conditions. Also, mussel production can produce habitat modification due to the accumulation of dead mussels that fall onto the bottom underneath the mussel rafts over years of production.

While mussel rafts can contribute to organic enrichment, they also play a role in nutrient cycling. Mussels filter-feed on particulate matter, including phytoplankton. This activity can enhance water clarity and influence nutrient dynamics in the surrounding water column.

The economy of the region is strongly dependent on its coastal communities. Because Galicia is one of the most important fishing regions in the European Union, Galicia is also the region with the highest employment and dependence on income from the fishing sector. There is additional high fishing pressure in the area from both artisanal and commercial fishers with around 3873 small scale or artisanal vessels and 518 coastal vessels, fishing a broad range of fish, crustaceans, and molluscs (Galparsoro et al., 2009; Surís-Regueiro & Santiago, 2014). In addition, mussel aquaculture, which is deeply embedded in local traditions, holds significant cultural and economic importance. In 2022, 219 698 tons were produced, with a value of 150 894 euros (<https://www.pescadegalicia.gal>). For these reasons, removing mussel rafts, a key component of sedimentary bottoms modification, is not a

feasible or desirable option. Additionally, we acknowledge the changing nature of habitats in the region, influenced by various anthropogenic activities and environmental factors, including climate change. Our approach is therefore to adapt to these evolving conditions and find sustainable solutions that balance ecological considerations with economic and cultural realities. While not restoring the sedimentary bottoms under mussel farms to their original state, modifying them serves as a form of ecological mitigation and an opportunity to enhance the overall ecosystem health while aiding the overfished populations of European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) to recover.

Restoration actions and benefits

Developing nature-based solutions in the form of artificial structures that are deployed below mussel farms in Vigo (figure 11) will help mitigate the impact of mussel farming on the benthic ecosystems and favour secondary production and recirculation of carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus to higher trophic levels. This will increase the resilience of the benthic communities by improving the complexity and heterogeneity of the benthic habitats. Increased and improved habitat complexity will also favour invertebrate and fish populations of commercial interest. Introductions of the European lobster in the systems affected by mussel farms will help the lobster population recover from overfishing and increase the capacity for biomitigation of organic matter through the feeding of lobsters on fallen mussels that accumulate under the mussel farms. It will thus open for possible integrated multitrophic aquaculture culture development.

Integrated multitrophic aquaculture is a sustainable aquaculture practice that combines different species in a way that allows the by-products (wastes) of one species to be used as inputs for others. In the context of mussel farms, integrated multitrophic aquaculture can help reduce the environmental impact of mussel farms as it will allow for species at higher trophic levels (e.g., lobsters) to utilize the nutrients that become available through the mussel farming, preventing nutrient buildup, and generate economic benefits. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture thus allows for the simultaneous cultivation of multiple valuable species. This diversification can provide economic benefits by creating additional revenue streams for aquaculture operators. For example, while mussels may be the primary product, the cultivation of lobsters can also generate income.

Promoting the recovery of lobsters below mussel farming could be essential for various reasons, not only economic, but also from the point of view of population conservation. European lobsters, particularly those in the early benthic phase (i.e., a post pelagic-larval juvenile state when lobsters settle on the seafloor), exhibit a preference for substrates with pre-existing shelter, like mussel shell interstitial spaces. These areas provide optimal conditions for lobster recruitment, development, and survival (Linnane et al., 2000). Adult lobsters are often associated with habitats at the boundary between sedimentary- and rocky-bottoms, coincident with seafloor depressions featuring a steep slope. Such locations, which are characterized by medium to high wave energy conditions, are suitable for lobster settlement (Galparsoro et al., 2009).

The rias of Vigo, despite having limited lobster populations, thus offer an opportunity for population recovery. Creating suitable habitats beneath mussel farms could provide an environment for lobsters to thrive and exhibit natural behaviours. Deploying artificial reefs provides a mix of soft and rocky bottoms, resembling natural lobster habitat, which can significantly contribute to the conservation and enhancement of lobster populations in the region. Creating more habitat heterogeneity under mussel farms may also increase the resilience of other commercial species, improve benthic

community structure by increasing biodiversity, and making the community more resilient to adverse conditions that may result from climate change.

Figure 11. Map showing the demonstration site in Vigo, Spain.

Local actors and key stakeholders

Government and administration stakeholders are the Port of Vigo, the Ministry of the Sea (“Consellería do Mar- Xunta de Galicia”), which provides permits, and the management authorities of the National Park of the Atlantic Islands of Galicia (“Parque Nacional Islas Atlánticas de Galicia”). Commercial and professional stakeholders are professional and recreational fishermen organisations including the Cangas fishermen association (“Cofradía de Pescadores de Cangas”), the San Martín de Moaña fishermen’s association (“Cofradía de Pescadores de San Martín de Moaña”), the San Juan de Redondela fishermen’s association (“Confradía de Pescadores de San Juan de Redondela”), the Presidency of the fishermen’s associations (“Fundación para la Pesca y el Marisqueo”), artisanal and recreational fishermen, mussel farmers, the Galician Mussel Regulatory Board (“Consello Regulador do Mexillón de Galicia”), mussel producers’s associations including the Producers’ organization of Mussel from Galicia (“Organización de produtores de Mejillón de Galicia”) and the Galician cooperative society of mussel producers (“Sociedad Cooperativa Galega Mexilloneiros de Galicia”), the wholesale business “Mejilloneras Cons de Udra”, which deals with wholesales of fish and aquaculture products, BlueStructures (a private company that provides artificial structures for benthic habitat restoration), the Galician Federation of Underwater Activities (“Federación Gallega de Actividades Subacuáticas”), SCUBA diving centres, the professional association of tourist guides of Galicia (“Asociación Profesional de Guías de Turismo de Galicia”), and the Nautical Cluster of the Ria of Vigo (“Clúster Náutico Ría de Vigo”). Recreational users are recreational fishermen, and SCUBA

divers. Relevant NGOs, research and educational stakeholders are the Association for Ecological Protection of Galicia (“Asociación para a Defensa Ecolóxica de Galicia”), Ecologists in action (“Ecoloxistas en acción”), the University of Vigo (“Universidad de Vigo”), the University of Alicante (“Universidad de Alicante”), the Platform for Protection of the Ria of Vigo (“Plataforma Defensa Ría de Vigo”), the Galician Institute of Aquaculture Training (“Instituto Gallego de Formación en Acuicultura”), the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, and the Institute for Marine Research (“Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas”). The latter two provide sensors and the receivers for lobster tagging.

Workshops and interviews

After an initial identification of the main stakeholders, government agencies, environmental organizations, local communities, researchers, industry representatives, and other interested parties were invited to several one-on-one meetings. In these meetings the objectives of CLIMAREST were outlined and the benefits of the collaboration for the different participants and for society. Stakeholders were first approached in person or through telephone interviews which were arranged mainly with the production sector, which requires personalisation of the planned interactions.

Mechanisms by which stakeholders may affect or be affected by restoration activities

Figure 12. Stakeholder diagram over lobster recovery and habitat melioration of the rias of Vigo, Spain. Pressures on the sedimentary soft bed ecosystem and lobster populations are represented within the red rectangle. Mitigation and rehabilitation actions (black lines and rectangles) consist of 1) deploying artificial reef structures, 2) tag and release juveniles of European lobsters (*Homarus gammarus*) and 3) outreach activities to inform the Spanish public. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and

NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

The demonstration site in Vigo (figure 11) consists of a 500 m² area beneath a mussel farm raft where an artificial concrete structure (1.2 x 0.7 x 0.6 m) has been deployed, and a 1000 m² reference area inside the marine protected area of the National Park of the Atlantic Islands of Galicia. For any activities to be possible in these areas permits and permission from the management authorities of the marine protected area and mussel farmers have been necessary. These are thus marked as key stakeholders (upper left, figure 12). In addition to the two areas in the marine protected area and under the mussel farm, two types of Thelma Biotel receivers (fastened to a bouy) have been installed: 13 receivers of TBR 800 and 6 of TBR 700L for tracking the movement of lobsters introduced to, or from, the area.

The primary concern of this demonstration case is the recovery of European lobster populations and the enhancement of the sedimentary soft bed ecosystem in the rias of Vigo. Pressures on the benthic ecosystem and the lobster populations are outlined within the red rectangle (top, figure 12). These include pollution, overfishing, and habitat degradation. To improve the benthic habitat, artificial reefs from BlueStructures (middle, figure 12) have been installed under a mussel raft to provide shelter for organisms that can make use of the waste and mussels that fall from the mussel raft (black box in the middle of figure 12).

To help the recovery of lobster stocks, tagged juvenile lobsters are released in proximity to the artificial reefs (black box to the left, figure 12). This work is carried out with the collaboration of local institutions with experience in the field, such as the Institute for Marine Research or other project partners such as the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (left side, figure 12). Both the Institute for Marine Research and the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research provide telemetry receivers for the preliminary examination of habitat use by adult lobsters or nearly adult juveniles in the areas beneath mussel rafts and close to the artificial reefs. Another actor that contributes positively to the monitoring activities is the Galician Institute of Aquaculture Training (lower middle, figure 12). The Galician Institute of Aquaculture Training both provides reared lobsters for the reintroductions, and it will have a key role in project outreach activities. It is therefore a key stakeholder.

In addition, professional and recreational fishers are key stakeholders as they may provide bycatch of wild lobsters for tagging and tracking (top left, figure 12). Besides contributing positively to the recruitment of tagged lobsters for the monitoring activities, which is key for evaluating the effect of the artificial reefs on lobster recruitment and population recovery, professional fishers could affect monitoring activities negatively by unintentionally removing or causing the telemetry receivers to move while fishing (top left, figure 12). Then again, they could also affect monitoring positively by reporting and giving receivers from captured lobster back to the researchers. This would allow for the recovery of important data (top left, figure 12).

The benefits of the restoration actions can be disseminated to environmental associations that are concerned about the quality of the marine environment and promote the sustainable use of resources in a scenario of global climate change (right side, figure 12). There is also the possibility of developing citizen science in partnership with diving collectives and associations (left side, figure 12),

and students from the universities of Vigo and Alicante (bottom, figure 12). Such actors could for example report on lobster observations in an App, thus contributing monitoring data.

Rocky subtidal ecosystems – Madeira, Portugal

Coastal context and sensitivity to disturbances

Macroalgae-dominated marine habitats are thriving ecosystems often found in shallow coastal areas comprising communities of diverse seaweeds. Macroalgae provide critical ecosystem functions by offering shelter and sustenance to a multitude of marine species. They create complex habitats for fish, invertebrates, and other organisms, contributing to overall biodiversity. Beyond their ecological significance, algae help maintain water quality by absorbing nutrients and providing oxygen through photosynthesis. These "marine forests" are essential for biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, supporting marine life and serving as crucial indicators of ecosystem health and resilience. In the Mediterranean Sea and Atlantic, a wide range of different macroalgae genera like *Cystoseira*, *Styppodium*, *Dictyota*, *Ericaria*, *Gongolaria*, and *Sargassum* are critical elements of benthic habitats.

Situated in the northeast Atlantic, the Madeira archipelago is heavily dependent on tourism and ocean-related industries, encompassing fisheries as well as maritime enterprises. Shallow marine ecosystems around the island are rocky reef habitats dominated by large habitat-forming multi-specific canopy stands formed by the brown seaweeds *Sargassum*, *Cystoseira* and *Gongolaria*. However, over the last decades, large parts of the island have undergone a phase shift towards barrens dominated by sea urchins (Bernal-Ibáñez et al., 2021; Gizzi et al., 2021). This decline of macroalgae-dominated habitats marks a major ecological loss for the island's coastal ecosystem, impacting many animal species relying on these marine forests.

Such phase shifts often occur with increased sea urchin grazing intensity as their feeding activity can play a significant role in these ecosystems' stability, biodiversity, production, and functioning. With several natural factors influencing the intensity of sea urchin grazing (e.g., population density, food availability, and predation pressure), anthropogenic pressures such as overfishing (and consequent reduction in sea urchin predators), coastal development (e.g., increased sedimentation, habitat destruction), pollution (e.g., marine litter, agricultural runoff), non-indigenous species and climate change can also favour the proliferation of sea urchins and the spread of barren grounds. Previous studies have shown that sea urchin barrens and macroalgae-dominated habitats exist in a delicate balance with the possibility of shifts and reversal between both states (Gizzi et al., 2021).

Around Madeira Island, the presence of the long-spined sea urchin, *Diadema africanum*, has been linked to the extensive existence of sea urchin barrens. Sea urchin barrens are characterized by an overabundance of sea urchins and a scarcity of macroalgae resulting in a less diverse and productive community with reduced biodiversity and biomass. Previous studies have shown that around Madeira Island, shallow subtidal communities reverse from sea urchin barrens to being macroalgae-dominated when *D. africanum* densities are below a threshold of about 0.5 sea urchins/m² (Gizzi et al., 2021).

Restoration actions and benefits

Macroalgae-dominated habitats play a crucial role in maintaining marine ecosystems, supporting biodiversity, and benefiting nearby communities. These habitats, dominated by various genera like

Sargassum, *Gongolaria*, and *Cystoseira*, provide numerous ecological advantages. Their importance goes beyond supporting biodiversity. They impact nutrient cycling, coastal protection, and even human well-being (e.g., for scuba divers and recreational fishers). Marine forests, rich in biodiversity, enhance the resilience and stability of ecosystems by offering complex habitats, shelter, and nursery grounds. This, in turn, supports commercial fisheries by influencing the recruitment and abundance of valuable species. Additionally, macroalgae contribute to oxygen production, improving water quality and stabilizing sediments to prevent erosion, maintaining seabed stability. Restoring degraded marine forests and promoting a phase shift from sea urchin barrens towards macroalgae-dominated habitats is crucial for the sustainability of marine ecosystems and the well-being of coastal communities in Madeira.

In Madeira, restoration activity focuses on two genera of native macroalgae that have recently undergone great declines in their biomass: *Sargassum* and *Cystoseira*. Active restoration activities will be conducted in four locations: 2 inside and 2 outside a marine protected area (Figure 13).

Planned restoration actions in Madeira are three-fold: (1) promoting macroalgae, (2) grazing control and (3) monitoring.

A comprehensive strategy is being developed to actively promote the proliferation of macroalgae by testing a series of different methods and setups. In the laboratory, recruitment and cultivation will be tailored to the specific needs of both algae species. For example, various substrates (e.g., ceramic, natural rock, terracotta) will be tested under controlled laboratory conditions to identify optimal conditions for macroalgae recruitment, attachment, and growth. Subsequently, the lab-cultivated algae will be transplanted to the restoration sites. This phase of the restoration process includes exploring modular artificial structures of various sizes, including the deployment of small units, larger panels, and/or the inclusion in living sea walls, to assess the efficacy of each approach. These real-world tests aim to ascertain the most efficient and environmentally sustainable transplantation methods, marking a crucial step towards successfully promoting and restoring macroalgae in natural habitats.

The long-spined sea urchin, *Diadema africanum*, has been identified as a key predator regulating macroalgae around the Madeira Island. Therefore, its presence will be monitored, and once the critical threshold of 0.5 individuals/m² is surpassed, grazing control methods will be tested (i.e., sea urchin removal).

Finally, it is paramount to have a periodic and reliable monitoring program to assess the effect of the restoration action on the local biodiversity. Algae and sea urchin diversity and abundance will be seasonally monitored at all restoration sites to accompany the progress of restoration actions and evaluate the necessity of grazing control methods. A full community survey was conducted in the beginning of CLIMAREST to establish a baseline and will be repeated yearly to assess the overall progress and changes in communities. Additionally, to aid the monitoring program, a mobile app has been developed that allow the monitoring of 24 species of ecological importance. The application is being used as part of a citizen science program which was established with the help of 10 diving centres in the island of Madeira and three in Porto Santo. The dive guides use the app during the debriefing with the dive clients and provide critical information on the abundance of the selected 24 species at their dive sites (Cebrian et al., 2021).

Figure 13. Map showing the demonstration site of Madeira. The restoration is occurring in four locations: two outside (A and B) and two inside (C and D) the marine protected area of Garajau.

Local actors and key stakeholders

Local government stakeholders are the Regional Directorate of the Sea (“Direção Regional do Mar”), the Institute of Forest and Nature Conservation (“Instituto das Florestas e da Conservação da Natureza”), and the Regional Directorate of Environment and Climate Change (“Direção Regional do Ambiente e Alterações Climáticas”). Commercial stakeholders are SCUBA diving centres (13 in total), Frente Mar Funchal which is the company in charge of public access to the sea (e.g., swimming pools and facilities along the rocky coastline), and hotels, in particular the ones with seafront access. Relevant recreational users are recreational fishers, tourists, and SCUBA divers. Educational stakeholders are marine researchers which includes researchers from The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation and the University of Madeira, and six to 18 years old students.

Workshops and interviews

A workshop focused on SCUBA diving centres was held on the 28th of February 2023 in the facilities of The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation. The workshop included the participation of five SCUBA diving centres represented by the owner and/or one employee. The workshop was structured in three parts. Firstly, one session of questions and answers was conducted with Mentimeter. During this session the following five questions were asked:

- 1) “How do you consider the seabed of Madeira?” – closed answers using a four points Likert scale from “Really unhealthy” to “Really healthy”.
- 2) “What are the biggest threats to the marine environment of Madeira?” – open answers.
- 3) “How could Madeira's marine environment be recovered?” – open answers.
- 4) “What are the most important species to monitor?” – open answers.
- 5) “What are the most exciting species for divers?” – open answers.

The following session of the workshop was an open debate about the answers from stakeholders followed by a presentation of CLIMAREST and an introduction to the restoration plan in Madeira. The last session of the workshop included two questions related to the practical use of the Dive Reporter App, developed by The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre - The Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation for divers to report species observations. These questions were:

- 1) “Would you participate in a monitoring program with this app?” – closed answers: “Yes”, “No”, “I don’t know”.
- 2) “Which interface do you prefer?” – closed answers: “Tablet”, “Kiosk” and “Web”.

During the month of March 2023, eight one-on-one meetings were conducted with the remaining diving centres since they preferred to be interviewed at their facilities. The modality of the individual meetings was the same as of the workshop held in February. The only difference was that the sessions of questions and answers was conducted with pen and paper instead of using Mentimeter.

Overall, stakeholders showed interest in participating in the monitoring program using the Dive Reporter App, they discussed the proposed restoration action, and gave their preferences on how they would like to be contacted in the future. They committed to using the Dive Reporter App to monitor the marine coastal ecosystem before and during the restoration activity. Moreover, SCUBA Diving Centres recognized the advantage of interacting with their clients using the app as a debriefing tool after each SCUBA dive in all the diving sites around the Madeira Island.

The interaction with the 13 SCUBA Diving centres is ongoing. The Dive Reporter App has been updated following the requests of the SCUBA Diving centres. Species that are not relevant for science, but which are exciting for clients have been added to the list. To incentivise the use of the Dive Reporter App, tablets with the app installed, were distributed to each of the SCUBA diving centres. An electronic kiosk was also developed to house the tablet and to make its use more attractive to SCUBA divers. After having seen the first prototype of the kiosk, SCUBA Diving centres that did not show interest in it during the first approach expressed a desire of having one in their facilities.

The Institute of Forest and Nature conservation was approached through a one-on-one meeting in which the objective of CLIMAREST was presented and the restoration plan for Madeira was described.

Mechanisms by which stakeholders may affect or be affected by restoration activities

Figure 14. Stakeholder diagram over macroalgae restoration in Madeira, Portugal. Pressures on the macroalgae rocky reef are represented within the red rectangle. Restoration actions (black lines and rectangles) consist of 1) assisting macroalgae recruitment, 2) control the population of grazers (e.g., sea urchins *Diadema africanum*), and 3) monitoring marine biodiversity. Stakeholders are classified in four categories and are illustrated in blue boxes following an increasing colour gradient from lighter blue to darker blue: Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs. Stars indicate priority stakeholders. Arrows are coded as: black connects restoration actions to the environment; grey indicates that the action (or the stakeholder) is influencing a stakeholder (or an action); green specifies that the link is beneficial, and red indicates a negative effect.

At present, in Madeira, there is no identified stakeholder that specifically represents a threat to the targeted marine ecosystems. To develop the restoration activity within the protected area, it is mandatory to have the permit of the Institute of Forest and Nature Conservation. They are thus a key stakeholder (lower middle, figure 14). Similarly, there is a need for permits administered by the Regional Directorate of the Sea and other authorities (lower middle, figure 14) to deploy any sort of equipment, such as recruitment panels for macroalgae to attach on to, and for any culling or removal of sea urchins while SCUBA or free diving.

The knowledge, expertise and facilities provided by marine researchers (middle, figure 14) are of paramount importance for the success of macroalgae recruitment on recruitment panels. Besides, this stakeholder group will be responsible for conducting dedicated surveys and monitoring programs to assess the effects of the restoration action and to verify that the number of grazers stay below the threshold that is needed for macroalgae to recover (Gizzi et al., 2021).

SCUBA diving centres and their clients (right, figure 14) will contribute by monitoring the effects of the restoration action using the Dive Reporter App. Moreover, these stakeholder groups will benefit from the restoration of the macroalgae habitat since we expect that this will improve ecological functions and increase the biodiversity of local marine communities making SCUBA diving experiences more attractive.

Hotels and Frente Mar Funchal (the company in charge of public access to the sea, e.g., in relation to swimming pools / facilities along the rocky coastline; lower left, figure 14) may interfere with the deployed living sea wall by complaining about the structures in front of their facilities. Currently it is impossible to predict such attitudes since these stakeholders have not been contacted yet.

Lastly, students, recreational fishers, and tourists (left side, figure 14) will benefit from the macroalgae restoration. An increase of the complexity and diversity of local marine communities, including an enhancement in abundance of marine species, will, hopefully, increase their knowledge and awareness about the marine environment and their willingness to protect it.

Initial interactions with stakeholders across the demonstration sites

Overall, 121 stakeholders were identified within the five demonstration sites. This number has increased significantly compared to the first assessment conducted in May 2023 (n = 41). We were able to fill the gaps identified during the first assessment like identifying relevant stakeholders from category i) regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site, and category iv) education, schools, research, and NGOs, in all demonstration sites and homogenising the number of representative stakeholders in the four stakeholder groups (table 1).

Table 1. Total number of stakeholders identified within each demonstration site/country, as a percentage by category per demonstration site/country, and overall total number of stakeholders identified per category across all demonstration sites/countries. Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs.

Stakeholder type, %	Norway	Ireland	France	Spain	Portugal	Overall
Category i	28.0	19.4	22.2	11.1	27.3	25.0
Category ii	36.0	32.3	33.3	37.0	27.3	41.0
Category iii	8.0	25.8	14.8	18.5	27.3	22.0
Category iv	28.0	22.6	29.6	33.3	18.1	33.0
Total number	25.0	31.0	27.0	27.0	11.0	121.0

By considering the potential influence and interest of the different stakeholders and how the restoration activities in each demonstration site might affect the different actors and their activities (c.f. König et al., 2021; Reed et al., 2009; Reed & Curzon, 2015), a total of 57 priority stakeholders were identified across the five demonstration sites (table 2). These have been marked by stars in the stakeholder diagrams (figures 2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 12, and 14).

Table 2. Total number of priority stakeholders identified within each demonstration site/country, as a percentage by category per demonstration site/country, and overall total number of stakeholders identified per category across all demonstration sites/countries.

Category i) represents the regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the study site. Category ii) includes commercial/professional users. Category iii) represents recreational users. Category iv) includes education, schools, research, and NGOs.

Priority stakeholder, %	Norway	Ireland	France	Spain	Portugal	Overall
Category i	33.3	25.0	50.0	15.4	25.0	17.0
Category ii	33.3	16.7	50.0	53.8	25.0	21.0
Category iii	5.6	41.7	0.0	7.7	25.0	8.0
Category iv	27.8	16.7	0.0	23.1	25.0	11.0
Total number	18.0	12.0	10.0	13.0	4.0	57.0

Most of the priority stakeholders represent commercial or professional users within the demonstration sites (category ii; 21%, table 2). For the most part (in 39% of the cases), the demonstration teams only wished for these stakeholders to be aware of the restoration activities. From a little less than one fifth of the stakeholders (17%) the demonstration teams wish to get their permission or approval to conduct the restoration activities within the demonstration sites. The demonstration teams also wish to engage equally large portions of the stakeholders (17%) in the actual restoration activities (e.g., for planting seagrass, releasing lobsters, or killing sea urchins) and in the outreach activities, respectively. Finally, the demonstration teams hope to engage a smaller portion of these stakeholders (11%) in the monitoring activities.

The second largest category among the priority stakeholders were those that represent regulation, administration, management, enforcement or harvesting of resources within the demonstration sites (category i; 17%, table 2). Stakeholders from this category were mostly sought after for permits that would allow for the restoration actions to take place (67%). To a lesser degree the demonstration teams wished for these stakeholders to simply be informed of the restoration actions (27%), or actively participate in the restoration actions (7%) or outreach activities (20%).

Priority stakeholders from NGOs and the educational sector, including schools and research (category iv; 11%, table 2), were largely sought after for active involvement in the restoration activities (60%). To a lesser degree these stakeholders have been contacted simply to be informed about the restoration activities (10%), or to be involved in monitoring (10%), or outreach activities (20%).

Priority stakeholders representing recreational activities within the demonstration sites (category iii) were the fewest (8%, table 2). Primarily these stakeholders are considered for active restoration activities (50%) or for awareness to coordinate recreational and restoration activities and endure as little conflict as possible (38%). To a much lesser degree these stakeholders are considered for monitoring or outreach activities (13%, respectively).

Up to the time of this report most stakeholders (68%) have been approached by CLIMAREST partners. Four modes of contact have been used: 1) formal invitation; 2) informal invitation (e.g., phone call or chat); 3) invitation through the collaboration of other stakeholders and, 4) invitation through social media. Overall, 51% of the stakeholders were contacted through informal invitations. In Madeira only, the most common approach to contacting stakeholders was through a formal letter (table 3).

Table 3. Percentage of types of contact used to approach stakeholders within each demonstration site/country, and overall.

Type of contact, %	Norway	Ireland	France	Spain	Portugal	Overall
Formal	0.0	23.1	2.9	11.1	27.3	10.6
Informal	27.5	66.7	76.5	48.1	18.2	51.7
Collaboration of other stakeholders	0.0	0.0	2.9	3.7	9.1	2.0
Social media advertisement	15.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
Not contacted yet	57.5	10.3	17.6	37.0	45,5	31.8

In 44% of the cases, CLIMAREST partners were able to meet with the selected stakeholder after one invitation. However, in some cases (10%) it was necessary to send several reminders or requests (i.e., more than 3 times) before engaging with the stakeholders.

Thus far, CLIMAREST partners have met most of the identified stakeholders across the five demonstration sites (59%). In a few cases (1.3%) it has been impossible to meet with the stakeholders yet, due to a lack of responses or time constraints. The most used mode of engagement so far (35.5%) has been through one-on-one meetings. However, this methodology is not the most adopted in all demonstration sites (Table 4).

Table 4. Percentage of stakeholder engagement mode used in each demonstration site/country, and overall.

How did you meet the stakeholder?, %	Norway	Ireland	France	Spain	Portugal	Overall
In a workshop with representatives from different stakeholder groups	27.5	38.5	5.9	3.8	0.0	19.3
In a workshop with representatives from the same stakeholder group	0.0	7.7	2.9	0.0	18.2	4.0
In a one-no-One meeting	12.5	43.6	67.6	34.6	9.1	36.7
Not possible to meet with this stakeholder	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.7	0.0	1.3
Not yet	60.0	10.3	23.5	53.8	72.7	38.7

For future engagement with the stakeholders, additional one-on-one meetings, workshops, and interviews have been planned. Over the following few months, other approaches that may be used to reach key stakeholders and the potential of different modes of engagement in subsequent stages of the restoration work will be explored.

Concluding remarks

In this report we have presented an initial stakeholder analysis based on site-visits, partner experience, scoping, qualitative workshops, and interviews in the demonstration sites. By identifying, assessing, and prioritizing local actors based on their potential to influence or be influenced by relevant restoration actions we have selected key stakeholders and issues to be included in subsequent restoration steps. So far, most of the priority stakeholders in the five demonstration sites have been contacted and for some sites the stakeholders are already involved in the restoration activities. In the next steps of CLIMAREST we will further elaborate on this work to develop best practice guidelines for stakeholder involvement in marine restoration activities.

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